

Quantum Mechanical Time as a Measure of Evolution of a Statistical Ensemble?

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In classical mechanics, $x(t)$ and all higher derivatives are known for a particle. Such is not the case of a quantum particle as it is stochastic, as is a particle in a statistical gas. Unlike a gas, however, there may be only one quantum particle, but a wavefunction comprising all possible momentum states (with their weights) is created with “time” removed completely. Thus, it seems a statistical ensemble is created in quantum mechanics as if there were many particles at the same time (although the normalization is 1). A quantum particle at a point x has various complex probabilities $\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ associated with different momentum p values. The evolution from one x to another is due to the stochastic nature of the potential $V(x)$, it seems. $V(x)$ itself is an average. It seems the potential may be responsible for the statistical nature of different momentum hits to a quantum particle. Thus, in quantum mechanics, one does not follow the time path of a particle as one does in classical mechanics, yet there is time in the Schrodinger equation even for a bound state. How is this explained? We argue this time represents the evolution of the statistical quantum ensemble and not the stochastic particle motion. In addition, “interference” also seems to be an average property (with time removed) because the interfering $\exp(ipx)$'s correspond to a quantum particle in different p states at different times (i.e. there should be no physical interference). The stochastic motion of the quantum particle, however, creates a resonance through the cycling of its stochastic values with a frequency and it seems such a particle should be sensitive to interactions with periodic objects such as a phonon and photon due to their frequency and not just energy alone.

Classical Versus Quantum Mechanics

In classical mechanics, a particle is described by $x(t)$. Thus, one knows exactly how it evolves from x_1, t_1 to x_2, t_2 under the action of $V(x)$. A quantum particle at point x_1 may be in one of any momentum states (including forward or backward motion) given by the probability $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. Such a particle interacts with $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ so the interaction outcomes are stochastic, but with weights related to $a(p)$ and V_k . One may calculate an average kinetic energy at x , but this average must be taken over a period of time, because the quantum particle is in a p_1 state at t_1 , p_2 at t_2 etc. Thus:

$$[\sum \text{over } p \quad p^2/2m a(p) \exp(ipx)] / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad \text{for a bound state ((1))}$$

Thus, kinetic (first term of ((1))) and potential energy and total energy are average quantities which take time to measure. They describe a statistical ensemble which may evolve or undergo cycling motion of the single quantum particle as in the bound state case.

Statistical and Quantum Mechanics

Statistical and quantum mechanics are similar in that the motion of a single particle is stochastic and that both try to measure average properties of a system. The statistical system is comprised of many particles and has average properties of T , volume, pressure etc. A potential $V(x)$ is not stochastic in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, rather the stochastic behaviour comes from two body scattering (or scattering with the walls). A single particle may have momentum p_1 at t_1 with probability $C \exp(-p_1^2/2mT)$ and p_2 at a later time.

The quantum bound system with one particle is stochastic because $V(x)$ is stochastic, so x is associated with the probability. Like with a statistical gas, one considers all different p states of a single particle at the same time (which is not really what occurs). (In the statistical gas, one may consider the various different particles having different momenta at a given time.) This gives a quantum “timeless” bound state theory with average values such as $V(x)$ and $KE(x)$ with a constant energy E at each x . A single particle with momentum p at x has a probability $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ and a kinetic energy $p^2/2m$, but its potential energy is not really defined, it seems, because it is subjected to stochastic hits from $V(x)$. Thus, energy E is an ensemble property. Thus, it seems that time is a property assigned to the quantum ensemble and not single particle motion. This quantum ensemble includes both forward momenta and backward momenta which classical occur at very different times in the bound state. For the quantum ensemble, however, all momenta occur at different times so there is no reason to separate forward and backward motion.

In quantum mechanics, $\exp(iEt)$ represents the time behaviour of the ensemble. Why should it be periodic? From $KE(x) + V(x) = E$, it seems that it takes time to evaluate these averages, but that does not yield periodic motion of an ensemble in time. The periodic motion in time seems to come from reactions of a particle with momentum p with the potential i.e. if $V(x)$ is written as $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$, then the Schrodinger equation for a single bound particle is:

$$a(p) p^2/2m + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = E \quad ((3))$$

This holds for all p and it takes time for the various $\exp(i(p-k)x)$'s to interact with V_k , in fact that time is $1/E$ for all p . Thus, there is a cyclical nature to the changes of $\exp(ipx)$ due to scattering with the stochastic $V(x)$. This seems to be the focus of quantum mechanics. Time represents the evolution of the ensemble and picks out any resonances which may occur. A bound state resonance has a frequency of $1/E$ ($\hbar=1$) which may couple to other objects such as phonons or photons which also have a frequency. Simply following the stochastic motion of a single quantum particle in time becomes complicated and does not show “average” properties quickly as the Schrodinger equation does, especially the cycling property.

Interference

Interference is often considered in quantum mechanics, but for a single particle what is interfering? There is only one particle. $P(p/x) = \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ is complex and one only sees interference effects upon combining one $P(p_1/x)$ with another $P(p_2/x)$, yet these occur at

different times. The $\exp(ipx)$ term is created through an interaction with $V(x)$ and is already a periodic type of function (hence the idea of a wavelength). It is also statistical in nature as it is part of a probability.

Time here, however, refers to the evolution time of a particle, not the evolution time of the ensemble used in the Schrodinger equation. For example, consider p and $-p$. Classically, the particle moves forward at t_1 and then returns at t_2 completing its cycle, yet these two momentum values give “interference” if $a(p)=a(-p)$ i.e.

$$p a(p) \exp(ipx) - p a(-p) \exp(-ipx) = 2p a(p) i \sin(px) \quad ((4))$$

Thus, for a fixed p , moving from one x to another has the appearance of “interference” in ((4)). Other interference results may be obtained e.g. for $p^*p/2m$ etc. The point seems to be that these p occur at different times, so where is the physical interference? Interference exists in the statistical ensemble (included in the wavefunction $W(x)= \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$ which does not account for different times for each p . Thus, quantum mechanics seems to describe average properties of ensemble and interference is one of these average properties.

It should be noted that the complex probability $a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$ is created by interaction with a potential which acts in a stochastic manner. Even for two slit interference and single slit diffraction, there should be interactions of a quantum particle with the material around the slits i.e. a potential. Trying to determine through which slit a particle passes seems to be equivalent to changing the potential and so leads to different experimental results.

Comparisons of Quantum Mechanics with Classical Mechanics

If quantum mechanics deals with ensemble averages of a stochastic particle, it is not completely clear why one creates objects such as wavepackets or compares high energy quantum mechanics to classical mechanics. Quantum mechanics does seem to have a particle which evolves in time, but in a stochastic manner even though $V(x)$ is the same for quantum and classical mechanics. One does not see attempts to take a particle in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas and compare it to a deterministic classical particle in a potential $V(x)$. For the MB gas, it is understood there is stochastic behaviour due to two particle scattering (or wall scattering). If quantum mechanics is also stochastic, one may focus on average properties of the ensemble and hope these give insight i.e. provide information about resonances which exist and their frequencies etc.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum mechanics deals with a stochastic particle with the stochastic behaviour emerging from the stochastic potential $V(x)$. $V(x)$ itself is an average. Thus, there is a $P(p/x)$ because $V(x)$ creates a momentum distribution at point x . All time (i.e. particle evolution time) is removed from this quantum statistical ensemble as one tries to examine average properties of the ensemble such as $KE(x)$, E and interference. Given that

different discrete average energy values may be found, one has different resonances. When time is added to the Schrodinger equation, this "time" seems to be related to the evolution of the quantum ensemble and not directly to single particle motion. For example, for a bound state the time evolution of the ensemble is $\exp(iEt)$ indicating a kind of periodic motion occurring as a particle interacts stochastically with $V(x)$. This t does not measure changes in say the momentum of a stochastic particle as it suffers one hit after another from $V(x)$ whereas classical mechanics does measure time this way. E in quantum mechanics is an average value and takes time to measure. Thus, there is time uncertainty associated with E . The single particle has a kinetic energy $p^2/2m$ and is knocked from one p state to another in a stochastic manner. If the quantum particle has a momentum p_1 at x , it is not clear what hit it will receive from $V(x)$ at x because $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. Any k hit may occur creating a very stochastic evolution, although one controlled by weights V_k . Like with statistical mechanics, it is too complicated to follow the motion of a single particle, so one considers an average of the different possible values (with all time removed). For a classical gas e.g. Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, one has many particles, i.e. replicas of the single particle and so considering an instant in time makes sense. In quantum mechanics, one has only one particle and has to create "mathematical" average quantities, with each term in the average taken at a different instant in time.